

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF AFRICAN CULTURE,
POLITICS AND DEVELOPMENT**

VOLUME 7, NO. 1 APRIL 2012

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF AFRICAN CULTURE, POLITICS AND DEVELOPMENT

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF AFRICAN CULTURE, POLITICS AND DEVELOPMENT

Published by Research on Culture and Development (Consult)

e-mail: infoafcudev@yahoo.com

ISSN - 0795 - 1469

Volume 7, No. 1, April, 2012

Editorial Manager

Dr. (Mrs) Enobong David Umoh

Associate Professor of Public Administration

University of Uyo, Uyo, Nigeria

08088519695

e-mail: umohenobong@ymail.com

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IMPACT OF THE END OF THE COLD WAR ON GLOBAL POLITICAL ECONOMY

Essien Ukpe Ukoyo Ukpe
Department Political Science
Akwa Ibom State University

Volume 7, No. 1, April, 2012

Abstract:

The collapse of the Soviet Union and the end of the Cold War and the consequent triumph of capitalism has had wide ranging implications for global political economy. This paper looks at the disadvantages as well as advantages of the end of the Cold War as it relates to the present global political economy. Among the disadvantages highlighted in the paper are growing income inequality both among and within nations, high chronic levels of unemployment in Western Europe and elsewhere, and, most of all, environmental degradation, widespread exploitation, and the devastating consequences for national economies wrought by unregulated international financial flows. Moreover, contradictions have resulted in the resurgence of North-South economic antagonism in the post Cold War era. Weaker economic nations are further put to the worst in the world system due to the high cost of economic globalization. The hopes of the early 1990s that growing international economic interdependence would provide the basis for a peaceful world order have not come to fruition. Despite these, however, the paper also discusses the advantages of the collapse of the Soviet Union and the end of the Cold War to include expansion of world trade and an increase in international competition due to a more highly integrated international financial system. This has increased the capital available to developing countries. Other benefits highlighted in the paper include growth in economic regionalism; reduction in inter-state conflicts; democratization of previously command economies; reduction in the use of force as a foreign policy tool and increase in international cooperation among major powers. The paper recommends a development-oriented and selfless leadership to harness local potentials to build strong economies which could compete favourably and benefit equally with other developed countries from the emerging global political economy.

Introduction

The year 1989 marked a critical point in the shaping of a new era in international political and economic relations between the former Western and the Eastern blocs in particular and the rest of the world states in the international system in general. For forty years, Europe had remained divided, Soviet Union maintained an empire that almost covered the entire Eastern

Europe while America created for itself the superpower role of protecting its allies in NATO and Asia (Kirkpatrick, 1990:1).

This was the characteristic of the Cold War period. The Cold War was a deadly conflict between the capitalist bloc and the defunct communist bloc, between the United States of America and the former Soviet Union and their allies where each side faced the risk of destroying the opponent as well as itself in the event that it embarks on a first strike action with its nuclear weapons.

In other words, the United States and the defunct Soviet Union were on a head on collision course! Both nations were prepared to fight a full scale nuclear and conventional war, but were not willing to risk the carnage of a full scale nuclear war. Due to this, both parties carefully avoided nuclear conflict with each other. The possible dangers of the initial nuclear exchange between the two former bloc leaders deterred both sides from using their nuclear weapons against each other.

Both nations stockpiled nuclear weapons, Weapons of Mass Destruction (WMD) and conventional weapons to deter each other or their allies from contemplating a pre-emptive attack against the other side. These weapons therefore served as deterrents and thereby prevented the outbreak of a nuclear war between the two powers.

Although, the United States and the Soviet Union were at war, yet they could not fight with each other even with the use of conventional weapons as the use of any type of weapon by one side against the other would have ultimately led to the use of nuclear weapons or an outbreak of nuclear war with appalling consequences.

All these were to change at the turn of the year as the iron curtain came down and the Soviet Empire collapsed under the hammer of Mikhail Gorbachev's *perestroika* and *glasnost*. This signaled the collapse of the Brezhnev Doctrine and the end of the Cold War. The result was the liberation of the countries of Eastern Europe, the collapse of the Berlin Wall and "... the progressive opening of borders between Hungary and Austria, Czechoslovakia and Austria, East Germany and West Germany" (Kirkpatrick, 1990:1).

Beyond these changes in Europe, the end of the Cold War resulted in formal end of hostilities between the two dominant ideologies (capitalism and socialism) and what Kirkpatrick (1990:4) called "... the constraints of the sustained global military preparedness imposed by the Cold War". It also led to the transformation of the world from bipolarity to unipolarity with the emergence of one center of power under United States' hegemony.

Other changes as enunciated by Ekpe (2012) include the globalization of trade and resultant rapid economic transformation; the spread of the capitalist dogma of liberalization; a shift in focus of debates in the United Nations General Assembly and Security Council from ideological considerations; reduction in the use of the veto power; erosion in the power of southern groups and NGOs like the Non-aligned Movement; isolation of despotic rulers like Mobutu Sese Seko of Zaire (now Democratic Republic of Congo); use of international criminal courts to arrest, try and sentence despots like Manuel Noriega of Panama, Jean Bertrand Aristide of Haiti, Augusto Pinochet of Chile, Slobodan Milosevic of Yugoslavia, and Charles Taylor of Liberia for drug trafficking, war crimes, abuse of human rights and crimes against humanity respectively; civil uprisings against despots in countries like Egypt, Algeria, Yemen, Syria, Tunisia, etc; institution of neo-liberal democratic governance which are characterized by recognition and enforcement of human rights; enforcement of the Rule of Law; openness and transparency; capacity building; accountability; zero tolerance to corruption, etc.

Statement of the Problem

The collapse of the Soviet Union and the consequent internationalization of the capitalist political economy has led to the diminution of the sovereignty of states in the international system. Before 1989, the presence of the Soviet Union provided a check on the imperialistic excesses of the United States of America.

At the height of the Cold War, the United States weighed the consequences of its actions against other states in the light of possible Soviet reaction, especially where such states were effectively aligned to the Soviet Union. It therefore could neither intervene indiscriminately in crisis in such countries nor impose her foreign policy on such states.

That has changed considerably after the end of the Cold War. According to Engdahl (2012), since the collapse of the Soviet Union and the nominal end of the Cold War some twenty years back, rather than reducing the size of its mammoth defense spending, the US Congress and all US Presidents have enormously expanded spending for new weapons systems, increased permanent military bases around the world and expansion of NATO not only to former Warsaw Pact countries on Russia's immediate periphery; it also has expanded NATO and US military presence deep into Asia on the perimeters of China through its conduct of the Afghan war and related campaigns.

Today, the United States can intervene in the domestic affairs of weak nations with impunity. By manipulation of the instrumentality of the United Nations, in 1989, the US intervened in Panama to oust Manuel Noriega; in 1990 it led in the deposition Saddam Hussein of Iraq; it facilitated the ouster of Jean-Bertrand Aristide of Haiti in 1991 and helped restore him back to power after extracting a commitment from him to stick closely to free-market economics; under the guise of humanitarian impulses, the US in 1999 intervened and bombed Yugoslavia. We would not forget how it improvised a makeshift peace in what was left of Bosnia and edged toward accepting the de facto partition of the country, its intervention in Somalia, its complicity in the long drawn war in Afghanistan and the issues of autonomy in the West Bank and Gaza between Israel and its Arab neighbors are some of the proofs of United States' brinkmanship in the post Cold War international politico-economic order.

Among the instruments it uses in some of the interventions above are economic sanctions, interference with information networks, "peace enforcement" and "friendly fire" -- nonlethal weapons.

United States' intervention has therefore become the defining feature of the present international order. This has the potential of undermining the political monopoly exercised by states over their territories and therefore deals a serious blow on states' sovereignty. With the USSR out of the way and the United States exercising unrestrained authority, the juridical claim by governments over their territories has become increasingly very difficult.

Under American leadership, both the industrialized and industrializing economies have been forced to lower trade and investment barriers. Eight rounds of multilateral trade negotiations under the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT), the principal forum for trade liberalization, have significantly decreased trade barriers. To satisfy the United States, more and more nations have been pursuing neoliberal economic policies such as deregulation and privatization. These developments, according to Gilpin (2001), have resulted in an increasingly market-oriented global economy.

Theoretical Orientation

This paper will be examined under the framework of America's policy of containment. One can not explain the Cold War without reference to the ideological conflict engendered by Soviet Union's communist expansionism and the United States' capitalist policy of containment. In line with America's perception of communism as a unified global conspiracy and Soviet Union as an "evil empire", the American doctrine of "containment" propounded by George Kennan, regard communism as a contagious disease whose spread must be controlled or stopped forcefully. Containment therefore sought to confine and restrain the spread of Soviet Union's doctrine of Communist Internationalism globally. This was done through various means including a European Recovery Program known as the Marshall Plan, the formation of a military alliance between the U.S. and Western European nations in 1949 called the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO), the creation of a Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) to gather detailed information about

Communist moves through espionage in foreign lands, building of military bases on ally territories to prevent such allies from falling into the hand of authoritarian Soviet control and the use of Breton Woods institutions like WTO, the World Bank and IMF to foster the conquest of the world economy through the imposition of capitalist doctrine of liberalization.

The policy of containment latter called "the Truman Doctrine" came to the fore following President Truman's pledge to support free peoples who are resisting attempted subjugation by armed minorities or by outside pressures and his subsequent grant of \$400 million aid to the Greek and Turkish governments to fight Communist subversion.

Containment succeeded in many instances to stem the tide of communist spread. For instance, in 1953, the United States, using the instrumentality of the United Nations successfully defended South Korea from a communist invasion from North Korea. In the threat from North Korea against South Korea in 2013, the United States unequivocally declared that North Korea can never be accepted as a nuclear power. This apparently is because North Korea is communist.

Containment also succeeded in the short term during the Vietnam War. The events of the late 1980s which could be summarily explained as the triumph of capitalism have proved that Kennan's prediction that the policy of containment would transform the identity and the behavior of the Soviet state was correct (Gilpin, 2001).

In 1989, the communist government of Union of Soviet Socialist Republic crumbled under the sledge-hammer of Gorbachev's *glasnost* and *perestroika*. This signaled the end of the Cold War. Although some authors have attributed the collapse of the Soviet Union to structural weakness within the Soviet Union, the activities of national forces and biting poverty in its economy and society, the Policy of Containment played a significant role as Gorbachev himself was a product of Western indoctrination.

The New International Political Economic Order

With the collapse of the structures which governed the conduct of international affairs for the past forty years, America was faced with the most far-reaching reorientation of its foreign policy since 1947 (Kirkpatrick, 1990:1). This brought about a new international political economic order. Scholars (cited in *International Political Economy and Globalization*) agree that the fall of Soviet Union created a unitary global political economy. In agreement with this thought, Gilpin (2001) believes that "the end of the Cold War provided the necessary political condition for the creation of a truly global economy".

However, Yilmaz (2008:44-45) argues that from a military/political point of view, the international system under American leadership is unipolar. But from an economic/political point of view, on the other hand, the international system can be said to be multipolar, rather than unipolar.

Throughout most of the last half of the twentieth century, the Cold War and its alliance structures provided the framework within which the world economy functioned. The United States and its major allies generally subordinated potential economic conflicts to the need to maintain political and security cooperation. Emphasis on security interests and alliance cohesion provided the political glue that held the world economy together and facilitated compromises of important national differences over economic issues. With the end of the Cold War, American leadership and the close economic cooperation among the capitalist powers waned. Simultaneously, the market-oriented world grew much larger as former communist and Third World countries became more willing to participate in the market system; this has been exemplified by the much more active role taken by the less developed countries (LDCs) in the World Trade Organization (WTO). While this development is to be welcomed, it has made the task of managing the global economic system more daunting (Gilpin, 2001).

Some scholars (cited in *International Political Economy and Globalization*) however argue that the participation of former communist and Third World countries in the global market is not as a result of rational acquiescence but as a result of Western incentives and sanctions that

pressured these developing states to "pursue trade and financial liberalization and to deepen their participation in the global economy".

Gilpin (2001) believes that the major economic achievement of the post-World War II era has been to restore the level of international economic integration that existed prior to World War I. However, he argues that "as national economies have become more and more integrated, the significance of the fundamental differences among national economies has greatly increased". That is why critics have adumbrated on the high cost of economic globalization which include:

growing income inequality both among and within nations, high chronic levels of unemployment in Western Europe and elsewhere, and, most of all, environmental degradation, widespread exploitation, and the devastating consequences for national economies wrought by unregulated international financial flows (Gilpin, 2001).

These contradictions have resulted in the resurgence of North-South economic antagonism in the post Cold War era. This is because growing economic globalization in the post-Cold War era does not appear to be breaking the historical stratifications between the North and South. Rather, it is economic globalization that channeled by past grooves of strong and weak growth. The national units already integrated into the world economy become more integrated into the world economy with the grim reality that weaker economic nations are further reduced to what Yilmaz (2008:52) calls "the low-growth ruts of the world system".

This is why Wenger *et. al.* (2003) argue that "the hopes of the early 1990s that growing international economic interdependence would provide the basis for a peaceful world order have not come to fruition. Instead, international politics has become highly complex and is marked by continuous change and a pervading sense of insecurity".

Despite this however, the collapse of the Soviet Union and the end of the Cold War has led to expansion in world trade and an increase in international competition due to a more highly integrated international financial system. This, Gilpin argues, has increased the capital available to developing countries.

While some scholars see the financial globalization as "a healthy and beneficial triumph of global capitalism" (Gilpin, 2001), others see it as the institution of confusion in the international economy. Quoting Bob Avakian, the Central Committee of the Revolutionary Communist Party, USA in its evaluation of the post Cold War era sees the period as one of "transition with potential for great upheaval".

Ideological Shift

As mentioned above, the United States and its major allies viewed every event in the world in the last half of the twentieth century from an ideological perspective and the need for the West to maintain preponderance and security cohesion in the face of communist threat. This was to change with the end of the Cold War. The forces of contending ideologies that had taken center stage for half a century gave way to a new, nascent international system. The United States had seemingly arrived at the apex of its global power: U.S. values, such as liberalism and democracy, spread around the globe (Wenger *et. al.*, 2003).

Gilpin (2001) argues that "... with the end of both communism and the "import-substitution" strategies of many less developed countries (LDCs), the relevance of Marxism greatly declined, and liberalism, at least for the moment, has experienced a considerable growth in influence" with more countries around the world adopting liberal principles and opening up their economies to foreign capital, reducing the level of state control over their economies and shifting emphasis to export orientated strategies.

Yilmaz (2008:44) writes:

The former rivals of the United States, especially the Soviet Union and China, have either collapsed or jettisoned the central features of their ideologies that were hostile to the United States. Other countries have turned to American military protection. The "American Empire" may best be seen operating in the Persian Gulf, Iraq, and the Middle East, in general, where the armed forces of the United States have established a semi permanent foothold and thousands of soldiers deployed at bases to keep a watch on Iran, Syria, and other "potential enemies".

Marxism only survives today as an analytical tool to evaluate capitalist growth as only very few impoverished countries still hold tenaciously to it. Even the Central Committee of the Revolutionary Communist Party, USA has agreed to the fact that with the triumph of capitalism, there has been significant growth in the world economy. They however argue that this has been accompanied by high levels of unemployment and underdevelopment and extensive dismantling of welfare state programs.

The Growth in Economic Regionalism

In the absence of the Cold War rivalry and the possibility of prostituting between the two super powers, developing countries are seeing the need for regional cooperation. Thus, one consequence of the end of the Cold War is the growth and spread of economic regionalism. This new regionalism has much greater significance for the global economy. Such economic cooperation arises from the discovery by the states of their shared political and economic problems in a highly interdependent and competitive world and the need "... to strengthen their autonomy, improve their bargaining positions, and promote other political/economic objectives", (Gilpin, 2001).

Increase in Ethnic Conflicts, Religious Militancy and Terrorism

One of the major developments in the post Cold War era is the increase in ethno-religious conflicts and international terrorism. It is argued that while classical inter-state wars tend to decrease in the post-Cold War era, there are many other serious threats to international peace beyond the full control of nation-states, most notably ethnic conflicts, religious militancy, terrorism, North-South conflict, and unfair economic competition, (Yilmaz, 2008:43).

While interstate conflicts have decreased considerably in the post Cold War era, ethnopolitical, religious militancy, terrorism, North-South conflict, and severe competition over scarce resources has intensified. Thus, the end of the Cold War can be said to have brought about both stability and instability to international relations (Yilmaz, 2008:43). Some scholars have argued that the intensification of these conflicts is a direct reaction to Western capitalist dominance of the global economy. Most of these reactions take place in the Islamic world. Although Yilmaz (2008:46) believes that such reactions currently appear to be disorganized, less powerful, and thus they are far away from posing a serious challenge to Western dominance, yet anti-Westernism in the Muslim world and elsewhere seems particularly to feed terrorism, a serious threat to peace in the post-Cold War period. To him, "terrorism, whether it is fed by religious fundamentalism or not, is another serious threat to peace in the post-Cold War era. While occasional terrorist activities have been part of human history, terrorism particularly became a

serious problem after the end of the Cold War, especially after the September 11 attacks". (Yilmaz, 2008:50).

Wenger, *et. al.* (2003:1) agree with Yilmaz that the September 11 attack is not unconnected with "...the resurgence of old civilizational fault lines and their underlying antagonisms in the absence of bipolar ideological conflict but rather the consequence of a palpable U.S. unilateralism and, by extension, Western military and political preponderance in the decade after the Cold War".

Another threat to peace in the post-Cold War period is rising religious militancy. Yilmaz (2008:50) believes that "religiously-driven conflicts have replaced the ideological zone of the Cold War as a serious source of international conflict" and that some analysts even contended that "it is now cultural rather than "iron" curtains that divide the world, and that religion fuels the conflict in a special way by inspiring intolerant and irreconcilable images of identity and commitment among competing civilizations".

Democratization of Previously Command Economies

The withdrawal of Soviet military presence from its former colonies in Eastern Europe and part of the Third World has enabled these nations which were previously run by Marxist dictatorial regimes to democratize their polities and this has led to the resolution of several conflicts that were fueled by the Cold War rivalry among Third World nations. However, those conflicts in the Third World in which the superpowers were not deeply involved during the Cold War have persisted after it, like the secessionist movements in India, Sri Lanka, and Sudan (Yilmaz, 2008:43).

The prevalence of these intra-national conflicts are mostly ethnically-driven conflicts over self-determination, succession or political dominance. These conflicts of ethno-political movements as have occurred recently in Eastern Europe (including the Balkans), Central Asia, Africa, and many other parts of the world have defied the ability of the nation-states (Yilmaz, 2008:48).

Wenger *et. al.* (2003) believes that the sharp increase of intrastate conflicts (as opposed to interstate conflicts) and the challenge to the sanctity of national sovereignty by the international community, constitute developments that have had, and continue to exert, significant influence on the conduct, nature, and understanding of international relations in the post Cold War world.

Reduction in the use of Force as a Foreign Policy Tool

The end of the Cold War has also reduced the emphasis on the use of force as an economic or military tool in international relations. This seems to challenge the realist perspective as military might seems to have run its course in international politics. This is evidenced by the reduction in military and defense budget of many countries excepting that of the United States of America which has not been considerably reduced as expected after the Cold War.

The reduction in the use of force in the international system is also manifested in the decline in the use of the veto power in the United Nations Security Council. Yilmaz (2008:46) shows that:

From 1945 to 1990, the permanent members of the Security Council cast the following number of vetoes: China, 3; France, 18; United Kingdom, 30; US, 69; and the Soviet Union, 114. Then between June 1990 and May 1993, there was no single veto. One exception occurred in May 1993 when Russia blocked a resolution on financing the peacekeeping force in Cyprus.

The end of the Cold War therefore has increased the capacity of the Security Council to reach agreement. This, according to Yilmaz (2008:46) is responsible for the increase in the number of peacekeeping operations in recent times.

Increase in International Cooperation Among Major Powers

One significant evidence of international cooperation among major powers in the post Cold War international system is the increase in the number of United Nations peacekeeping operations. Yilmaz (2008:46) identified only 13 peacekeeping operations between 1948 and 1978 and none within the ten years following. But from 1988, the numbers of peacekeeping operations have increased with 24 created between May 1988 and October 1993. This number almost tripled as of December 2008 as the numbers of peacekeeping operations reached 63 with 18, involving a total number of 112,660 personnel still in operation as at 2008.

The activities of the United Nations peacekeeping forces have even gone beyond the traditional peacekeeping to involve many peace building activities such as monitoring, even running local elections, assisting in the reconstruction of state functions (Yilmaz, 2008:49)

Increase in United States Influence in the Middle East

Starting with its intervention in Kuwait in 1990 through the instrumentality of the United Nations, the United States' influence in the Middle East and the Caucasus which was previously under Russian sphere of influence has increased after the Cold War. Yilmaz (2008:46) argues that in the absence of a counter power, the United States have increased its hegemonic influence in the Middle East as evidenced by its military operation in Afghanistan and invasion of Iraq in 2008. Moreover, the overthrow of Moumar Ghadafi of Iraq would not have been possible without US support.

In this post Cold War era, both NATO and the European Union have expanded their influence into former Russian colonies in Eastern Europe. It is a known fact that in 2004, eight formerly-communist countries, Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia, Poland, Hungary, Slovenia, Slovakia, and Czech Republic became members of the European Union while Bulgaria and Romania, other two previously-communist states became full members in 2007.

Conclusion

This study has revealed that the influence of American capitalist doctrine of liberalism has become epidemic in the post Cold War international system. The adoption of this policy has been beneficial to stronger economies while it has been detrimental, in fact, destructive to weak economic nations.

The economy of weak nations would crumble if entirely left to influence of external market forces. That is why some economic agents will favour government intervention – rather than market-oriented governance – in domestic economies (Mosley, 2005). Unfortunately, globalism is bringing about a world economic system where goods and services, investment, finance, and technology would flow across national borders without hindrance and their prices would be determined by forces outside the target market.

In reality therefore, continued progress in the integration of the world economy would render national governments less relevant. States would continue to lose their “powers not only to influence macroeconomic outcomes and to implement social programmes, but also to determine strategies for managing the industrial economy” (Weiss, 1997).

Recommendations

From the conclusion arrived in this paper, it is discovered that nation-states would therefore become helpless in the face of a growing global economy. It is therefore pertinent that every Third World nation with weak economies should urgently harness their resources to build strong economic bases for their countries before opening up their economies to the international market economy if they are going to survive the global holocaust.

For this to be possible, the weak nations need first and foremost selfless leadership that is committed to the development of their countries. Such development would however not be

possible without the leadership first breaking the economic ties with which their former colonial powers subtly tied the economies of their former colonies to the Western capitalist economy.

Nigeria and other weak economic countries of the South can only achieve self-reliance through autochthonous development. Continued over reliance on the West would result in continued underdevelopment and a consequent inability to compete favourably within the world capitalist economy. Local industries must be encouraged to grow through subsidies from the government, tax relief, government patronage of their products and selective imports to ensure that the superior brand of goods produced by local industries are not imported as this will reduce the demand for those manufactured locally and thereby affect the particular industry adversely. The government must pay particular attention to export-oriented industries in this regard.

In the same vein, the government must systematically control the type of foreign investment they allow into their countries to ensure that only investments that would be beneficial to the country would be allowed in.

Finally, the policy of indigenization and equity shareholding must be modified to make it mandatory for foreign conglomerates to source a higher percentage of their raw material inputs and labour internally. The Asian Tigers adopted similar strategies and this led them to successfully build up their economies (Owugah, 2003:250-252).

It is the belief of this paper that if these are done, it would strengthen Nigeria's economy and the economies of the developing countries and place them in a position to compete favourably with and benefit equally with other developed countries in the emerging world economy.

References:

- Central Committee of the Revolutionary Communist Party, USA (1999). "Notes on Political Economy". Retrieved from http://revcom.us/a/special_postings/poleco_e.htm on March 26, 2012.
- Ekpe, Aniekan (2012). Class Discussion during lectures on Pol 741: Contemporary International System, Political Science Department, University of Uyo, Uyo (unpublished).
- Engdahl, F. William (2012). "The One World Government's China containment strategy". Retrieved on October 23, 2012 from *Before IT's News @* <http://beforeitsnews.com/eu/2012/08/the-one-world-governments-china-containment-strategy-2447784.html>
- Gilpin, Robert. (2007). "Understanding the International Economic Order" in Princeton University Press. Retrieved from <http://press.princeton.edu/chapters/s7093.html> on March 26, 2012.
- International Political Economy and Globalization. World Scientific Publishing Co. Pte. Ltd. Retrieved from <http://www.worldscibooks.com/economics/6889.html>.
- Haass, Richard N. (February 17, 2006). "Sovereignty and Globalization" in *Project Syndicate: Council on Foreign Relations*. Retrieved on June 18, 2011 from <http://www.cfr.org/experts/afghanistan-iraq-us-strategy-and-politics/richard-n-haass/b3350>.
- Kirkpatrick, Jean J. (1990). "Beyond the Cold War" in *Foreign Affairs*. Vol. 69, No. 1. New York: Council on Foreign Relations Inc.

- Mosley, Layna. (2005) "Globalization and the State: Still Room to Move?" *New Political Economy*, Vol. 10, No. 3, September 2005 (Routledge Taylor & Francis Group).
- Milner, Helen (1998). "International Political Economy: Beyond Hegemonic Stability." *Foreign Policy*, No. 110, 1998 Spring. Retrieved from <http://www.mtholyoke.edu/acad/intrel/milner.htm> on March 26, 2012.
- National Intelligence Council (2007). "Nonstate Actors: Impact on International Relations and Implications for the United States". Conference Report. Retrieved from National Intelligence Council Website at http://www.dni.gov/nic/confreports_nonstate_actors.html on March 26, 2012.
- Owugah, Lemuel (2003). "Nigeria and the Globalization Projects" in Otoabasi Akpan Umana (ed.) *The Art and Science of Politics: Essays in Honour of Alhaji Ghali Umar Na'Abba* (Port Harcourt: Footsteps Publications), pp. 250-252.
- Veseth, Michael Friday, What is International Political Economy? (2007). Retrieved from International Political Economy Zone <http://ipezone.blogspot.com/2007/02/what-is-international-political-economy.html> on March 26, 2012.
- Waisbord, Silvio & Nancy Morris. "Rethinking Media Globalization and State Power". Google Books: Rowman & Littlefield.
- Wenger, Andreas and Doron Zimmerman. (2003). *International Relations: From the Cold War to the Globalized World*. Boulder: Lynne Rienner Publishers.
- Yilmaz, Muzaffer Ercan. (2008). "The New World Order": An Outline of the Post-Cold War Era" in *Alternatives: Turkish Journal of International Relations*, Vol. 7, No. 4, Winter 2008.